

The Results of Studying the History of the Tribal System in the Khorezm Oasis

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 10 Sep 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Oct 2024; **Published:** 11 Nov 2024

Abstract: The first stage of studying the culture of the Neolithic tribal community of the Khorezm oasis corresponds to the end of the 30s - the second half of the 40s of the twentieth century. The results of the study are reflected in the works of S.P. Tolstov, including an article published abroad. In the article is devoted to the historiography of the Joytun and Kaltaminor cultures of the Neolithic period.

The study of the history of the agricultural system in the Khorezm oasis has been consistently developing. The results of the research have been utilized not only in scientific works but also in new educational literature and books aimed at a wider readership.

In the article is focused on the analysis of the Khorezm oasis's socio-economic relations, clan-tribe association and the history of management, foreign relations, beliefs and spiritual culture.

Key words: Neolithic period, Jonbos 4, "Kaltaminor Culture"

Introduction.

The Khorezm Oasis is located on the right and left banks of the Lower Amu Darya, in the Turan lowlands between the Karakum and Kyzylkum deserts. In geography, this area is referred to as the "Southern Aral Sea Region," and it includes the lands of Karakalpakstan, Northern Turkmenistan, and the Khorezm region.

Due to the variability of the Lower Amu Darya branches, three ancient riverbeds – the Akchadarya, Sarykamysh, and Aral Sea delta channels – emerged at different times. Their banks were studied from paleogeographical and archaeological perspectives by members of the Khorezm Archaeological Expedition, and the results of these studies were published in a special monograph.

According to the available data, the Amu Darya began to flow into the Aral Sea through the ancient Akchadarya riverbed around 22,000 years ago, during the middle of the Upper Paleolithic period. By the Mesolithic period, the Amu Darya was directed westward from its left bank. The Davdon and Daryolik riverbeds formed a large lake in the Sarykamysh lowlands, with its waters flowing through the ancient Uzboy riverbed, crossing the borders of the Karakum and flowing into the Caspian Sea.

Methodology

Systematic analysis, historicity, and objectivity methods were used during the study of problems related to the emergence of the tribal breeding system and the forms of the clan system, as well as the results of the study of the history of the tribal system in the Khorezm oasis.

Results.

In ancient times, due to the migration of the Amu Darya, meaning its course changed, numerous small lakes and water bodies formed around the riverbeds. For this reason, the paleogeography and paleoecology of the Aral Sea region in the earliest periods differed from the modern geographical conditions. Currently, the Aral Sea region, Sarykamysh, and the areas surrounding the dried-up Uzboy riverbed were sufficiently supplied with drinking water in the earliest periods of history. Such conditions created favorable opportunities for humans to gradually colonize various regions, utilize natural resources, and develop cultural (anthropogenic) landscapes.

In the Khorezm Oasis, the Khorezm Archaeological Expedition, which began its research in 1938 with members such as S.P. Tolstov, Y.G. Ghulomov, and E.A. Polyakov, particularly focused on these aspects. According to S.P. Tolstov, the history of the human adaptation of the directions and basins of the Lower Amu Darya riverbeds is a complex issue, and “the history of the Amu Darya has been initially correctly described by the great Khorezmian scholar Abu Rayhan Al-Biruni”. This issue was addressed in a special article by Y. Ghulomov.

In 1939, a Neolithic site known as Jonbos 4 was discovered in the sandy lowlands of the Akchadarya river basin of the Amu Darya. In the following years, a group of such sites that were found and studied was united under the common name “Kaltaminor Culture”. As a result of the research, it was determined that the environment of the area, which is now modern natural geography of the Southern Aral Sea region, was completely different in ancient times. According to S.P. Tolstov, the delta of the Akchadarya was “a rich land with abundant reed and shrub forests, numerous river channels, and lakes, where the fishermen and hunters of Neolithic Khorezm built their dwellings.”

Later, important scientific data regarding the ancient human settlement in the desert, the characteristics of natural resource use, the significance of natural-geographical conditions in the development of agriculture, the interaction between humans and the environment, and paleoecological issues were obtained on a Central Asian scale by researchers such as S.P. Tolstov, A.S. Kes, Y.G. Ghulomov, A.V. Vinogradov, M.A. Itin, and E.D. Mamedov.

The well-preserved remnants of dwellings and archaeological finds beneath the clay and sand layers of the Jonbos 4 site allowed for the reconstruction of the lifestyle and culture of the Neolithic agricultural community in the Khorezm Oasis, dating back to the 5th-4th millennium BCE.

A Neolithic dwelling belonging to the archaeology of Central Asia and the history of primitive societies was reconstructed for the first time, characterized by a large hut covered with reeds and supported by wooden pillars. In the center of the Jonbos 4 dwelling, a large hearth was identified, along with traces of several smaller hearths used for cooking. Surrounding these hearths were fragments of ceramic vessels, tools made of stone and bone, bones of ducks, pigs, and other birds that swim in water, as well as numerous fish bones, including those of carp and catfish.

The reason for a somewhat broader discussion of this information is that the archaeological data identified at the Jonbos 4 site opened new avenues for studying the history of the agricultural system in the Khorezm Oasis. According to S.P. Tolstov, in the investigated site, the late stages of the maternal lineage—matriarchal period—were represented, where several pairs of close relatives from a large maternal family lived together.

In the Kaltaminor culture, a community of 100-120 people, including children, lived together as a kinship group. A large sacred hearth that burned continuously was considered the center of social life, around which community traditions were practiced.

The first stage of studying the culture of the Neolithic agricultural community in the Khorezm Oasis corresponds to the late 1930s and the second half of the 1940s. The results of these studies were presented in S.P. Tolstov's works, including an article published abroad.

As a result of the research conducted in the Lower Zarafshan basin, Neolithic settlements have been

discovered. Among them, in the Darbozaqir site, traces of a rectangular dwelling in a right-angled shape were identified. It resembled a hut covered with reeds and was supported by vertical wooden columns, reconstructed as a simple shelter. In reconstructing such dwellings related to the Kalaminoz culture in the form of huts, S.P. Tolstov utilized ethnographic data. For comparison, information is provided about the unique forms of huts found in tribal communities that have preserved primitive lifestyles and cultural traditions in Oceania and South Asia. As a result, it was concluded that in the Darbozaqir site, there were paired families consisting of 30-35 individuals related to a maternal lineage.

From a theoretical-methodological perspective, the Morgan-Engels theory was applied to study the history of kinship systems. This is broadly reflected in the chapters devoted to kinship society in the primitive history of Central Asia, emphasizing that in matriarchal communities, women held a higher status compared to men. Evidence highlighting the social and economic role of women includes not only child-rearing but also activities such as gathering, collecting and storing firewood, maintaining the fire in the household hearth, preparing food, cleaning animal skins, and other tasks.

In archaeological literature, primary importance is given to studying settlements and dwellings, tools made of stone and bone, pottery, and other artifacts. The topics of socio-economic relations and external contacts typically follow the description of archaeological issues and are covered in articles and monographs. This approach can also be seen in collaborative works summarizing Central Asian archaeology.

A.V. Vinogradov made a significant contribution to the study of Neolithic archaeological sites in the Khwarezm oasis. This is evident not only in the discovery of numerous sites from this period and the creation of maps of the monuments but also in their excavation and the acquisition of new materials.

In the 1960s and 1970s, A.V. Vinogradov, E.B. Bizhanov, and V.N. Yagodin conducted archaeological work in the Ustyurt region of the southwestern part of the Aral Sea area. As a result, traces of seasonal settlements and stone tools from the Paleolithic, Mesolithic, and Neolithic periods were found. These discoveries made it possible, for the first time, to link the human occupation of the Aral Sea region to the Late Paleolithic period. This indicates that hunter communities adapted to living in desert conditions.

In the chapter titled "Hunters and Fishermen of the Neolithic Period" in his monograph, A.V. Vinogradov notes that scientific data is limited in determining the transition of Neolithic communities to productive economic sectors in other parts of Central Asia, including steppe and mountainous regions, in comparison to the Jeitun culture, which developed in the southwestern part of Turkmenistan in the 6th-5th millennia BCE on the basis of farming and domestic animal husbandry. He discusses these issues separately. According to the researcher, archaeological evidence suggests that productive economic sectors emerged in the Khwarezm oasis around the mid-2nd millennium BCE and in the Lower Zarafshan basin around the turn of the 3rd-2nd millennia BCE.

This idea was first proposed by the researcher in an article from the 1950s and remained unchanged until the publication of his monograph. Later, in a monograph published abroad, which covered the Paleolithic to Early Iron Age archaeology of Central Asia, the section titled "Kalaminoz Culture in Khwarezm and Kyzylkum" did not discuss the primary economic activities of the Kalaminoz people. Instead, the book focused on issues such as the natural geographic conditions, descriptions, and chronology of sites in Khwarezm and Kyzylkum.

At one time, S.P. Tolstov suggested that the kinship communities in the Khwarezm oasis transitioned to animal husbandry in the final stages of the Neolithic period. G.F. Korobkova supported this idea, writing that the ancient communities living in the southern Aral Sea region and the Kyzylkum borders practiced animal husbandry from the early stages of the Neolithic and agriculture in its later stages.

In the 1980s and 1990s, research conducted in the Lower Amu Darya basin and Ustyurt led to an expansion of knowledge about the material culture of the Stone Age in the Aral Sea region, with new monuments being examined. At a site known as the "Tolstov Settlement," the remains of two Neolithic dwellings were identified, and materials found in Southern Khwarezm were published. Additionally, for the first time in the Khwarezm oasis, tools from the Late Paleolithic period were discovered on the western

slopes of Sultan Uvais Mountain, located on the right bank of the Amu Darya.

Discussion.

Thanks to the discoveries, it became possible to periodically identify the processes of appropriation of the Khorezm oasis by ethnic communities, as well as to study the stages of the development of the natural-geographic significance, human interaction, and cultural landscape of the region.

It should be noted that in 2005, research was conducted in the Kyzylkum region by international archaeological expeditions from Uzbekistan and France, and Uzbekistan and Poland (M. Khojanazarov, F. Brunet, Q. Shimchak). Additionally, artifacts from the ancient Stone Age were obtained from the southern foothills of Sultan Uways Mountain. In the next phase of research, tools from the Upper Paleolithic period were collected from the Kokcha site in the Khorezm oasis and the southern slopes of Sultan Uways Mountain by B.K. Saifullaev, M.M. Khojanazarov, and D.M. Jorakulov.

In the first quarter of the 21st century, as a result of a significant expansion of scientific information regarding the Kaltaminor culture in the Southern Aral Sea, Kyzylkum, and Lower Zarafshan regions, N.O. Khalmatov's work examines the dating and chronology of materials found in the Lower Zarafshan sites as a separate section, focusing on the agricultural practices and lifestyles of ethnic communities. The development of the Kaltaminor culture in the region is marked by the late 7th millennium BCE to the mid-4th millennium BCE.

In a co-authored work dedicated to the history and culture of Khorezm, V.N. Yagodyn discusses the timing and routes of the spread of the earliest humans in the Stone Age in the Southern Aral Sea, as well as the economic activities of ethnic communities and the forms of these activities.

In U.I. Abdullaev's research, the sources and historiography of primitive systems in Central Asia are analyzed, focusing on the economic and cultural types of the Stone Age, the regional distribution and economic development of the earliest agricultural and pastoral communities in the region, as well as important issues such as tribal organization and social governance.

H.O. Matkarimov's work discusses the development of anthropogenic landscapes and historical-cultural processes in the southern Aral Sea region, as well as the issues related to the historical reconstruction of the Neolithic period. Additionally, in the monograph prepared in collaboration with co-authors, the section written by U.I. Abdullaev and H.O. Matkarimov examines the process of reconstructing the social-economic system of the Neolithic period in Central Asia, including the Khorezm oasis. They analyze the significance of the natural environment and geographical conditions, characteristics of the spatial distribution of settlements, tools of labor and household items, the size of dwellings, and the remains of paleofauna and flora, elaborating on the essence of these factors.

In another section of the aforementioned work, N.U. Kholmatov mentions that the hunters-fishers and gatherer communities of the Kaltaminor culture not only lived in the Southern Aral Sea region but also spread to neighboring areas such as the Ustyurt, the banks of the ancient Uzboy river, the eastern Caspian coast, the territory of Western Kazakhstan, the Inner Qizilqum, and the borders of the Lower Zarafshan oasis, drawing attention to the unique characteristics of this culture.

The study of the history of the agricultural system in the Khorezm oasis has been consistently developing. The results of the research have been utilized not only in scientific works but also in new educational literature and books aimed at a wider readership.

Conclusions.

In the 1990s, archaeological monuments from various stages of the Stone Age were discovered, expanding the scientific data available for examining the history of primitive communal systems in the Southern Aral Sea and Ustyurt regions. Thus, from the early 21st century onwards, utilizing archaeological data related to periods not covered in written sources as historical resources and analyzing them from a historical perspective has gained particular importance.

In general, it is worth noting that there is no comprehensive research dedicated to the history of the kinship system in the Khorezm region and its subsequent ancient periods that is interconnected and generalized in terms of chronology and the development of historical processes.

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